

IMPROVING LISTENING SKILLS IN THE EDUCATION OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS.

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Abstract. Teaching students to listen is challenging yet rewarding skill that all teachers need to know. Listening and retaining information are two of the most important facets of teaching. Learning tips and tricks for the classroom for the applicable age and grade level are vital for a successful teaching experience. Teachers learn a wealth of ideas from other teachers. Experiences, strengths and background knowledge from fellow teachers are all effective in sharing techniques that work. Many of these ideas are listed in the 10 strategies to help student listen.

Key words: Listening, interactive, content, teaching, competition activity, discuss with students.

Early childhood and elementary classrooms require constant decision-making and instance structure to employ effective teaching strategies. Strategies that help students listen are imperative in lower grades. This article is about improving students listening skills. We all have moments when trying to get our children’s attention feels like talking to brick wall. At home, this inability to listen can be infuriating – and at school, it could be getting in the way of the learning. Listening is one of the most important skills for primary school children to master, but it doesn’t always come easily, especially in the early years of school. But with a bit of work, you can help your child develop their listening ability, with knock-on improvements at school. The study describes a system of training of listening within the most effective exercises; learning of listening becomes a part of developing the system of education.

Early childhood and elementary classrooms require constant decision-making and intense structure to employ effective teaching strategies. Strategies that help students listen are imperative in lower grades. Whether your child a voracious reader or is horrified at the suggestion of picking up a book, audiobooks could have some surprising benefits. Lucy explains how they could boosts literacy skills, and shares our pick of the best to get you started. If you have got some long journeys planned over the holiday period, chances are you have already considered investing in some story CDs to stave off boredom. But audiobookare not just useful on the move; they are also a brilliant tool for boosting your child’s reading skills.

“Listening to a story can be valuable for all sorts of reasons “, says Irine Picton of the National Literacy Trust. “One benefit of audiobooks is that children have the opportunity to hear speech patterns and rythms that they might miss in print. They teach them about them voice and expression, which can help with their own speaking and articulation “. Dialects, accents and humour are brought to life, providing children with a model for reading aloud. All children can benefit from listening to audiobooks, but they may be of particular advantages to reluctant

readers. “If a child find decoding or comprehension difficult, audiobooks, can make literature more accessible”, says Irine. “They get to hear the story in real time, rather than it becoming disjointed as they struggle through the text. It gives them the opportunity to become absorbed in the book”.

Audiobooks can also help children who find reading tedious. “They are great for restless children because they can be doing something else at the same time”, Irine explains. “It is quicker to listen to a story than to read it yourself, so they get a faster pay-off”. Plus University of Memphis research shows that we are more likely to preserve with an audiobook that does not immediately grab us than we would with a book, so they could help built stamina for stories if your child loses interest in books quickly. So audio books might have slightly fusty connotations, but children’s versions are far from boring, thanks to celebrity narrators such as Stephen Fry, Anne Hathaway and Matt Lucas. “ A good narrator can transform the story, and enjoyment of it”, says Laurance. “There is something about being read aloud to that never fails to be comforting, regardless of your age”.

I think children should be enabled to listen to and simple understand conversations in everyday life. Teachers should provide children with opportunities to listen to and speak in English through conversations. What should we do to build on children’s listening skills and further develop them? I think we have to find easy ways of improving listening skills in primary classes. As an English teacher we have to develop children’s interest in learning English through interesting interactive listening skills at our English lessons. Singing songs together is a catchy way to teach children language. Choose a song that has rhythm, rhyming and repetitive lyrics. The following activities always are used by me at my lessons. They are: Activity 1. Listen and sing songs. Objective: to improve pupils’ listening skills

Teacher plays the DVD. Teacher asks the students to listen to the song. Teacher asks the students to hold up pictures of farm animals as they sing the song together so that our students can associate the image with the word. After singing the same song a few times, we may ask our students to make a pause so my students can sing the lyrics without my help. We should help our students make up his/her own rhyming sentences and sing them together to memorize new words and definitions. The children's songs «Old MacDonald Had A Farm» is easy for students to learn and uses simple vocabulary and universal animal sounds that all children will recognize, no matter what language they speak. Activity 2. Look, listen and repeat. Objective: to improve pupils’ listening skills. Teacher sticks different flashcards on the blackboard and asks the students to look at them and listen to their pronunciation and repeat the words after him/her. Then teacher takes out the first one and asks the students to repeat from the beginning. Teacher takes out the second one, the third one and etc. By this way teacher will achieve the result.

Teacher can do some pre-listening and then have students listen to the text and perform a variety of tasks. Teacher evaluates students’ comprehension based on the correctness of their responses and proceeds to the next activity. Teacher implicates here is the focus on the result, the product of listening in the form of correct answers. This approach tests students’ listening comprehension, informing them that they failed at certain points, but does little to teach how to listen, that is, to help them understand what went wrong with their listening and how it could

be repaired. How often do teachers rush to supply a “correct” answer when a student fails to respond to a listening task? Teachers may play a recording several times and ask for other students’ input to make things right, missing an opportunity to determine the reason for the listening error. To revise this approach, a teacher could identify problems by making a note of students’ lapses in comprehension as she checks their answers. She would then discuss with students how they arrived at a certain answer, what prevented them from understanding parts of the text, and what could be done to improve their listening facilities. Finally, she would follow up with activities that target specific listening problems that emerged during the discussion. At present, it is important to involve children in language learning, given that there are great opportunities for learning English throughout Uzbekistan. It is advisable to teach language to children not from school age, but from preschool. However, because young children have low reading ability, enriching their knowledge by listening to them can be very effective.

To sum up I came to this conclusion if you are teaching a song or telling a story, don’t stay on that song or story the whole class time. We should follow up the song or story with a related TPR activity to keep the momentum of the class going. Then have students play a quick game in pairs. As shown in this brief example, varying the types of activities also helps to keep young learners interested.

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